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Adherence, acceptability and feasibility of post-discharge malaria chemoprevention (PDMC): synthesis report

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Adherence, acceptability and feasibility of post-discharge malaria chemoprevention (PDMC)

Synthesis report

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3 SUMMARY

This document briefly summarises the contextual factors of post-discharge malaria chemoprevention (PDMC) based on data from one delivery mechanism trial in Malawi and two nested qualitative studies that focus on caregivers' perceptions and community health workers.

A 5-arm, cluster-randomised delivery mechanism trial of PDMC with DHA-piperazine to be provided at 2, 6, and 10 weeks post-discharge was conducted in Malawi among children <5 years recently discharged from hospital after recovery from severe anaemia. Community-based delivery of PDMC, where caregivers were given the drugs for all three PDMC courses at discharge, resulted in higher adherence than facility-based methods where the caregivers had to go back to the hospital to collect the PDMC courses three times. PDMC has a high degree of acceptability among caregivers, but long distances entail that facility-based delivery is costly, which can have a negative effect on equity. Reminders given through community health workers and text messages had some but limited effect on adherence. To a large extent, caregivers viewed their child's public health card, where hospital staff had noted the dates for the caregivers to administer PDMC, as adequate.

4 INTRODUCTION

This synthesis report summarises a 5-arm, cluster-randomised delivery mechanism trial of post-discharge malaria chemoprevention (PDMC) among children <5 years hospitalised with severe anaemia at Zomba Central Hospital in Southern Malawi [1], and two nested qualitative studies on acceptability and feasibility PDMC)[1-3]. One of the two nested qualitative studies focused on the perspectives of female caregivers who had a child who was part of the trial [3], while the other focused on the perspectives of community health workers (CHW) who had been involved in the trial [2]. Data collection for the two studies was carried out in Zomba, Malawi, in 2016 and published in 2018.

5 THE DELIVERY MECHANISM TRIAL

Study participants (4-59 months old) were children hospitalised for severe anaemia who had received at least one blood transfusion [1]. They were required to receive the antimalarial drug dihydroartemisinin-piperazine (DHA-PIP) at 2, 6 and 10 weeks post-discharge. The trial compared community-based vs facility-based delivery of PDMC and used five study arms. The primary outcome measure was adherence to all treatment doses of dihydroartemisinin-piperazine, and this was assessed by pill-count done by field workers during home visits.

In the *community-based* study arms, the caregivers received all the drugs at the hospital when the child was discharged and received one of the following aids to remember to treatment dates:

- Arm 1. Exclusive use of the child's health card
- Arm 2. Text message reminder
- Arm 3. Visit from Community Health Worker

In the *facility-based* study arms, caregivers were instructed to collect drugs at the hospital for each of three PDMC courses. They received one of the following aids to remember to treatment dates:

- Arm 4. Exclusive use of the child's health card
- Arm 5. Text message reminder

5.1 RESULTS

Poisson regression was utilised for analysis. RESULTS: Between March 2016 and October 2018, 1460 clusters were randomised. A total of 667 children were screened, and 375 from 329 clusters were eligible and enrolled from the hospital. Adherence was higher in all three community-based compared to the two facility-based delivery (156/221 [70.6%] vs. 78/150 [52.0%], IRR = 1.24, 95%CI 1.06-1.44, $p = 0.006$). This was observed in both the SMS group (IRR = 1.41, 1.21-1.64, $p < 0.001$) and in the non-SMS group (IRR = 1.37, 1.18-1.61, $p < 0.001$). Although adherence was higher among SMS recipients (98/148 [66.2%] vs non-SMS 82/144 [56.9%]), there was no statistical evidence that SMS reminders resulted in greater adherence (IRR = 1.03, 0.88-1.21, $p = 0.68$). When compared to the facility-based non-SMS arm (control arm), community-based delivery utilizing CHWs resulted in higher adherence [39/76 (51.3%) vs. 54/79 (68.4%), IRR = 1.32, 1.14-1.54, $p < 0.001$].

5.2 DISCUSSION

Community-based delivery of dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine for post-discharge malaria chemoprevention in children recovering from severe anaemia resulted in higher adherence compared to facility-based methods.

6 QUALITATIVE STUDIES

6.1 BACKGROUND AND METHODS

Data collection for the two qualitative studies was organised separately and carried out by two different researchers. All interviews and FGDs were conducted in Chichewa, were transcribed in the original language, and then translated.

The study of *female caregivers* included participants from all five study arms [3]. 30 semi-structured in-depth interviews (six caregivers in each study arm) were conducted at the participants' homes. Five focus group discussions (one for each study arm, with 5-10 participants in each) were conducted at the hospital where the children had received treatment. The great majority of the caregivers, close to 70%, were subsistence farmers and lived in rural areas. The FGDs had a special focus on comparing the benefits and barriers of the different delivery and reminder systems.

The study of *community health workers* (CHWs) focused on study arm 3 [2]. In the Malawian health care system, CHWs are known as Health Surveillance Assistants (HSAs) and are paid a monthly salary by the Ministry of Health. In this report, we will refer to this cadre as CHWs. 20 individual in-depth-interviews (IDIs) and 2 focus group discussions (FGDs) were conducted with 39 CHWs who had been given the responsibility of conducting home visits to remind caregivers to give the medication to their child at the three intervals. The caregivers had received all the medication when their child was discharged. On the day of discharge, the CHW responsible for the catchment area of the affected child received their contact details and was informed about the participant and the location of their home.

One or two days prior to the scheduled date of drug administration, the community health worker was expected to receive a short message service (SMS) reminder on his/her phone to go to the child's home to remind the caregiver to administer the study medication. The CHW did not receive any other reminders or memory aids during the follow-up. They were not paid specifically for this work because it was considered to be part of their regular duties and because the study aimed to mimic real-life implementation.

6.2 RESULTS

6.2.1 Acceptability

6.2.1.1 Caregivers

Almost without exception, caregivers shared positive views on the trial drug and its effectiveness. There was a high degree of self-reported compliance with treatment guidelines in both community- and facility-based study arms. Only a few stated that they missed a treatment course. Several factors might have contributed to the high level of compliance. Caregivers had recently experienced how severe anaemia detrimentally impaired their child's health and well-being, which generated a feeling of fear that functioned as a driving force for treatment compliance.

A factor that may have influenced the reported compliance is the fact that a member of the study staff visited the participant's home to do pill counts after each treatment course. The expectation of these encounters might have enhanced treatment adherence.

6.2.1.2 Acceptability among community members who were not part of the trial

The study only included caregivers who had a child in the trial, but two CHWs specifically mentioned that as much as the caretakers whose children were receiving PDMC were happy to give medication to their children, some neighbours were curious and suspicious, suggesting to caregivers that the medicine might be harmful.

6.2.1.3 Community health workers

None of the CHWs had prior knowledge that there is a medication that can be given to children to protect them from getting malaria. Still, all of them, including the non-adherent, perceived PDMC as an important and beneficial intervention that would save the lives of many children.

6.2.2 Feasibility

6.2.2.1 Involvement of community health workers

Although the community health workers reported a high level of intrinsic motivation, adherence to the required number of home visits was very poor, with only one in four CHWs reporting full adherence. Positive factors for adherence were the knowledge and perception of the effectiveness of PDMC and the recognition from the community as well as the health system. Reported barriers to adherence by the CHWs included poor training, lack of supervision, high workload, and technical and structural difficulties. CHWs would have liked to receive more training, and several were embarrassed that the caregivers had more knowledge about the medication than they did.

Adherence was highest among CHWs who knew the location of the family that they were to visit.

Caregivers reported an even lower adherence by CHWs than the CHWs themselves did. Most stated that they received no visits but still remembered to give the medicine to their children. Some characterised CHWs as lazy and negligent, whilst others shared an appreciation of CHWs and described them as helpful and generous.

A few CHWs reported that caregivers feared raising unwanted suspicion among their fellow community members as to why they were being repeatedly visited by the CHW, which could result in being stigmatised.

6.2.2.2 Reminders via text messages

Both caregivers and CHWs reported not receiving *all* the text messages. Overall, CHWs reported that the SMS reminders were unnecessary due to their unreliability. While caregivers did not receive all

the SMS reminders, they nevertheless preferred to get SMS reminders themselves (as in arm 2 and 5), rather than SMS reminders to be sent to the CHW only (as in arm 3).

6.2.2.3 *Use of health cards to remember treatment dates*

Every child in the trial had a national public health card with the written dates for the required PDMC treatment courses. The great majority shared positive attitudes towards using the health card to remember treatment dates, and a high number of informants insisted they could be self-dependent and administer drugs to their children without reminders.

6.2.3 Equity

The two qualitative studies were not specifically designed to capture issues related to equity. However, several of the findings are relevant to the question of equity as summarised below.

6.2.3.1 *Facility-based delivery methods*

Among all the participants, approximately 66% lived 1-2 hours from the hospital, 25% lived 2.5-3.5 hours away, and close to 10% lived more than 4 hours away. Caregivers in the facility-based arms reported that travelling to the hospital to collect the medicine three times was costly and time-consuming. As a result, many caregivers generated extra income by doing extra labour or selling belongings, and some were forced to borrow money and had problems paying back.

6.2.3.2 *Text messages*

For study participants who did not own a phone, the text message reminders had to go through neighbours and/or family members, which entailed delays.

6.2.3.3 *Health cards*

Nine of the 64 informants (14.1%) reported to be illiterate, and a few caregivers said that low literacy was a potential challenge to using the health card. Nevertheless, many informants argued that it was easy for those with limited primary school education to find a family member or friend who could read the health information for them.

6.3 DISCUSSION

6.3.1 Acceptability

In contrast to IPTp, IPTi and SMC (IPTc), the PDMC (IPTpd) programme is directed towards a smaller population of seriously ill patients. These patients have already established connections to health staff after a recent hospital admission. PDMC is therefore perceived as a “natural” continuation or follow-up treatment, and results from this qualitative study show that it is well-accepted among caregivers. Even though their children seem healthy, caregivers in the programme understand the value of giving preventive malaria drugs in the post-discharge period. The fear of reliving past experiences where their children suffered from severe malarial anaemia seems to be a driving factor for treatment adherence. Our findings support a previous study that showed high caregiver acceptance of DHA-PIP in malaria treatment of young children in Malawi [4].

6.3.2 Involvement of community health workers

Previous studies on SMC have shown how the involvement of community-based health workers in Sub-Saharan Africa positively affects drug uptake. At the same time, many challenges have been identified that may impair CHWs motivation and work performance (for references, please see Nkosi-Gondwe et al 2018, page 2). Our studies support these findings. CHWs report a heavy workload, lack of supervision and limited financial incentives. Only one in four were adherent to the task given to

them in the trial (visiting caregivers and reminding them to provide the drug to their child). CHWs were supposed to receive a text message with instructions from study staff, and faults in this communication pathway can also explain the lack of visits. Additionally, the willingness of CHWs to adhere is possibly limited by the fact that they receive no additional remuneration for doing reminder visits.

6.3.3 Reminders via cell phones

Most caregivers prefer text message reminders rather than CHW visits. It should be noted that both CHWs and caregivers in arm reported that they did not receive all SMS reminders, so this system did not function as planned. In addition, several caregivers did not own a phone.

6.3.4 Health card

Our findings indicate that the national health card is the most secure, reliable, and easily accessible tool for health-related information. It is viewed as the unwavering source of information on dates for treatment courses, and most caregivers use it as their primary tool of reference. In addition, exclusive use of the health card has the advantage of not adding extra costs to caregivers or the health system.

6.4 CONCLUSIONS

The two qualitative studies revealed a high degree of acceptance towards malaria chemoprevention given as post-discharge management of children treated for severe anaemia. Community-based delivery was perceived as considerably more favourable than facility-based delivery due to fewer financial concerns. Community-based delivery is thus a better way to ensure equity.

Results from the five-arm cluster randomised trial recently confirmed higher adherence among caregivers who were part of the community-based study arms compared to those who had to go to the facility to pick up the drugs.

As for different forms of reminders for caregivers who had received all the drugs when their child was discharged (community-based arms), adherence to home visit reminders by Community Health Workers was very poor. Thus, the involvement of CHWs in the scale-up of PDMC does not seem to be feasible in the Malawian context. Text messages may be a more feasible strategy for reminding caregivers of treatment dates than visits from CHWs. However, not all caregivers own cell phones, and during the trial, neither caregivers nor CHWs received all the text messages. A central finding is the high acceptance of using the conventional, old-school health card with recorded treatment dates and medical history.

7 REFERENCES

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